

Ribopores

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How cells, organelles, and organisms communicate and sense their environment is a fundamental question in biology with implications ranging from cancer to planetary homeostasis. To the best of my knowledge, the identity of endogenous, *in vivo* gas-sensing nucleic acids are still unknown.¹⁻⁴ Due to the role of diffusion of gases across cell and organelle membranes, gas (solute) sensing and homeostasis in cells and organelles has to be tightly coordinated. Gases can also pass through channels such as aquaporins that also act as gasporins.^{5,6} A question arises why are aquaporins or other major channels are only protein-based? If “ligands” can be various different classes or factors such as gas, temperature, steroid, acid (retinoic acid, amino acid), proteins, RNA, and etc., why channels cannot be comprise of other molecules as well? Synthetic DNA-based pores and channels has been reported.⁷⁻⁹ But if humans can make DNA-based pores in a lab based on the knowledge generated in a matter of few generations in competitive “academic environments”, did millions of year in evolution fail in making similar pores in more resource competitive environments? It is challenging to ignore the possibility of polymeric nucleic acids (or perhaps even other classes of biomolecules) acting as pores or channels. As the diversity of nucleic acids and its modifications are highly complex, identification of endogenous ribopores and deoxyribopores (RNA and DNA-based pores, respectively) will be essential to understand some of the complexities of gasocrine signaling. Finally, since some ion channels can act as gasoreceptors, ribopores and deoxyribopores may also act as riboceptors and deoxyriboceptors, respectively.^{10,4}

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